

Synthesis of 2-(3'-pyridyl)-Y-pyrano-Benzofurans and 3'-hydroxy-2-(3'-pyridyl)-Y-pyrano-Benzofurans

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A few 2'-(3'-pyridyl)-Y-pyrano-benzofurans (IVa-c) and 3'-hydroxy-2'-(3'-pyridyl)-Y-pyrano-benzofurans (Va-c) were synthesised from *o*-hydroxyacetyl benzofurans.

BENZOFURAN and furano chromones have been known to possess various pharmacological activities¹⁻⁴. Khellin—a furanochromone is well known for its physiological activity⁵⁻⁷. The synthesis of pyrano benzofurans-khellin analogs-with 3-pyridyl substituent at 2 position in pyrone ring, was undertaken with the expectation that it will modify the activity of khellin itself.

Pyridine-3-aldehyde on condensation with *o*-hydroxy-acetyl benzofurans in presence of a base yielded propan-1-ene-3-ones (I), which were converted into the corresponding substituted 2'-(3'-pyridyl)-Y-pyrano (7, 8-e) benzo furans (IVa), 2'-(3'-pyridyl)-Y-pyrano (7, 6-e) benzofurans (IVb) and 2'-(3'-pyridyl)-Y-pyrano (5, 6-e) benzofurans (IVc) by refluxing them with SeO₂ and amyl alcohol. These compounds (IV a-c) were also synthesised by an alternative route. The base catalysed esterification of *o*-hydroxy-acetyl benzofurans with nicotinoyl chloride yielded *o*-(3'-pyridiloxy)-acetyl-benzofurans (II). Baker-Venkatram transformation of these esters (II) yielded the corresponding propane 1 : 3 diones(III) which on cyclization gave the corresponding 2'-(3'-pyridyl)-Y-pyrano-benzofurans (IVa-c).

Propan-1-ene-3-ones (I) on subjecting to Algar-Flynn-Oyamada reaction conditions gave the corresponding 3'-hydroxy-2-pyridyl-Y-pyrano benzofurans (V a-c).

The melting points, crystallisation solvents, percentage yields, etc. of I, II, III, IV and V are given in Table 1.

Physiological activity :

The compounds were tested for antiviral activity, anthelmintic activity and gastric acid secretion pylorus ligation activity. None of the compounds showed these activities.

Experimental

o-Hydroxy-acetyl benzofurans were prepared by earlier reported methods⁸⁻¹⁰.

General procedures for the preparation of :

Propan-1-ene-3-ones (I) : To a solution of pyridine-3-aldehyde (0.3 mole) and *o*-hydroxy-acetyl-benzofuran (0.2 mole) in ethanol (30 ml) was added slowly a solution of KOH (50%, 5 ml) maintaining the temperature below 25°. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3.4 hrs and it was then poured over crushed ice containing acetic acid. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with NaHCO₃ solution (5%) and crystallized from a proper solvent.

2'-(3'-Pyridyl)-Y-pyrano-benzofurans (IV a-c) : A mixture of propan-1-ene-3-one. (0.003 mole), SeO₂

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF PROPAN-1-ENE-3-ONES(I), o-(3'-PYRIDILOXY)-ACETYL-BENZOFURANS(II), PROPANE-1,3-DIONES(III), 2'-(3"-PYRIDYL)-Y-PYRANO-BENZOFURANS(IV) AND 3'-HYDROXY-2'-(3"-PYRIDYL)-BENZOFURANS(V)

Sl. No.	o-Hydroxy-acetyl benzofurans used	Corresponding Compounds									
		I		II		III		IV		V	
		m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %
(1)	6-Hydroxy-7-acetyl 3-methyl-benzofuran	171 ^a	90	141 ^g	80	153 ^g	80	211 ^f	80	198 ^e	50
(2)	6-Hydroxy-7-acetyl 5-ethyl-3-methyl-benzofuran	138 ^e	80	96 ^a	60	118 ^d	50	234 ^f	70	183 ^d	60
(3)	6-Hydroxy-5-acetyl 3-methyl-benzofuran	115 ^e	90	143 ^e	50	105 ^b	30	232 ^f	30	330 ^e	40
(4)	6-Hydroxy-5-acetyl 4,7-dimethoxy-benzofuran	80 ^c	95	79 ^b	70	91 ^b	60	182 ^f	20	212 ^e	70

* All compounds showed satisfactory C and H analysis.

a—Crystallised from 40% acetic acid ;
b—Crystallised from 50% acetic acid ;
c—Crystallised from 60% acetic acid ;

d—Crystallised from 70% acetic acid ;
e—Crystallised from 80% acetic acid ;
f—Crystallised from dioxane and
g—Crystallised from benzene.

(1 g) and amyl alcohol (14 ml) was refluxed for 10 hrs. in an oil-bath at 150°. The solution was filtered hot and amyl alcohol was removed by steam distillation. The resulting solid was crystallised from a proper solvent.

3'-Hydroxy-2'-(3"-pyridyl)-Y-pyrano-benzofurans (V a-c) :

A solution of propan-1-ene-3-one (0.0014 mole) in methanol (15 ml) was added to an ice-cold solution of sodium hydroxide (16%, 2 ml) followed by dropwise addition of H₂O₂ (15%, 2 ml). The reaction mixtures was kept in an ice-chest overnight and filtered. The alkaline filtrate was acidified with acetic acid and precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from a proper solvent.

Esters (II) : To an ice-cold solution of o-hydroxy-acetyl-benzofuran (0.035 mole) in dry pyridine (10 ml), nicotinoyl chloride (0.04 mole) was added dropwise with stirring. The mixture was stirred for 7 hrs at room temperature and then poured over crushed ice containing acetic acid. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with NaOH (2%) and crystallised from a proper solvent.

Propane-1,3-diones (III) : A mixture of ester (0.025 mole), powdered KOH, (3.4 g) and dry pyridine (15 ml) was stirred vigorously for 6 hrs. It was then poured over ice-water- and neutralised with acetic acid. The solid thus obtained was

filtered, washed with water and crystallised from a proper solvent.

2'-(3"-Pyridyl)-Y-pyrano-benzofurans (IV a-c) : To an ice-cold solution of propane-1,3-dione (0.04 mole) in chloroform (40 ml), conc. H₂SO₄ (10 ml) was added slowly with stirring. The mixture was stirred further for 30 min at 20° and poured over ice-containing NaOH. The chloroform layer was separated and product was isolated by evaporation of the chloroform. The resulting solid was crystallised to form a proper solvent.

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